

SALMONELLA SPECIE AND TOTAL VIABLE BACTERIAL LOAD IN ROASTED CHICKENS SOLD IN JOS-
NIGERIA

Carol Okoli¹, Okonji M.C², Ugoh S.C², Okolo S.N¹, Okoli A.C³, Alu A.J⁴.

¹Paediatrics Department, University of Jos, ²Federal School of Medical Laboratory Sciences, Jos. ³Kolac Medical Laboratories Jos, ⁴Jos University Teaching Hospital

ABSTRACT

The study was to investigate for the presence of *Salmonella* specie and total viable aerobic bacterial load in roasted chickens sold in Jos. The study was carried out on twenty five chicken samples. No salmonella specie was isolated from the samples. However, other bacterial organisms were isolates, viz: 9(36%) of the samples yielded *E.coli*; 5(20%) yielded *Citobacter* species; 3(12%) yielded *Proteus* species and 6(24%) yielded *Klebsiella* species while 2(8%) showed no growth. An average total viable aerobic bacterial load of 7.9×10^7 organisms per gram were counted from the samples. It is therefore considered that the roasted chickens sold at road sides in Jos could constitute serious health risks.

KEYWORDS: *Salmonella* specie; total viable bacterial; roasted chickens.

INTRODUCTION

Domestic Fowl (*Gallus domesticus*) known for its high rate of egg production is the most common specie in the tropics, however, bacterial infection of these birds is common and cannot be over emphasized Oluyemi and Robert, (1979).

The bacterial infection not only cause economic loss but could act as a source of food poisoning to the public.

High rate of salmonella infection of living chickens has been reported in various parts of the world, for instance, in Spain *Salmonella* specie was isolated from raw chicken after swabbing, Anon, (1990).

This could be as dangerous as bird flu if not properly diagnosed and treated. The species *S. gallnerium* and *S. pullorum* are the most frequently incriminated in poultry infections, Frobisher and Feuts, (1982) which if consumed by humans at an infective dose could produce infections especially in infants and debilitated persons, Libby, (1975) and Vernon *et al*, (1984).

Roasting may not totally eliminate the pathogen bacterial in the chicken coupled with the fact that other viable opportunistic bacteria might be present. This therefore, increases the risk of bacterial infections of the consuming public and consequently death if not properly diagnosed and treated.

This therefore calls for a closer attention in public health. It is in the light of this, that the present study is undertaken to investigate the presence of *Salmonella* specie and total viable bacterial load in roasted chickens sold in Jos-Nigeria.

OBJECTIVES

To investigate for the presence of *Salmonella* specie in roasted chickens sold at the road sides in Jos.

To determine the total viable aerobic bacterial load in same-day prepared roasted chicken sold at the road sides in Jos.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Jos is the capital city of Plateau State, situated in the middle belt zone of Nigeria with a land area of about 6 square kilometers and a population of about 3.3million with a fairly high proportion of the population involved in poultry farming. (Plateau State Land and Survey Report 1999).

The chickens parts were purchased at different road side spots located in Jos. The chicken samples were processed and cultured, Old (1996), Collee *et al*, (1996) and Collee and Marr, (1996). They were cultured for *Salmonella* species in Selenite-F- medium and Deocychollate agar at 37°C for 24hours. Plates showing growths were subjected to macroscopic, microscopic and biochemical examinations depending on their growth patterns and reactions. Plates showing no growth were re-incubated and at the end of another 24 hours designated 'no growth' if no growth was seen.

The viable aerobic bacterial count was done using Miles and Mistral method, Sheffield, (1996).

RESULTS

TABLE 1: The sample number and percentage of the bacterial isolates

BACTERIAL ISOLATES	ROASTED CHICKEN	
	NUMBER	%
<i>Salmonella</i> species	00	00
<i>E. coli</i>	9	36
<i>Citrobacter</i> species	5	20
<i>Proteus</i> species	3	12
<i>Klebsiella</i> species	6	24
No Growth	2	8
TOTAL	25	100

TABLE 2: Total viable aerobic bacterial count.

BACTERIAL LOAD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	NUMBER OF SAMPLES
9.6×10^3	2
4.6×10^4	2
3.3×10^5	1
6.2×10^5	1
3.4×10^6	1
1.5×10^6	3
1.0×10^7	7
2.1×10^7	4
1.4×10^8	1
4.5×10^8	2
7.6×10^8	1

A total of twenty-five chicken samples were used for this study. Table 1 shows the sample numbers of bacterial isolates from each of the samples. No *Salmonella* specie was isolated, however, other bacterial organisms were isolated viz: 9(36%) of the samples yielded *E. coli*; 5(20%) yielded *Citrobacter* specie; 3(12%) yielded *Proteus* specie and 6(24%) yielded *Klebsiella* specie while 2(8%) showed no growth.

Table 2 shows the total viable aerobic bacterial count in the samples. The lowest and highest limit were 10^3 and 10^8 respectively count of 1.0×10^7 organism/gram has the highest frequency of seven (7) samples. The mean viable aerobic bacterial load was 7.9×10^7 organism/gram.

DISCUSSION

Salmonella species are known to infect poultry among other animals. Available evidence in Nigeria indicates a lower *salmonella* infection rate in living chickens Gianella, (1981).

The absence of *Salmonella* in the roasted chickens discovered in this study agrees with that of Antiong and Udoh, (1968) in Calabar but disagrees with the report of Alonge and Oyekola, (1982) in Ibadan. The reason for this difference may not be conclusively established but could be that the roasted chickens used in this study were prepared from chicken not infected by *Salmonella*.

However, this does not establish the bacteriological safety of these meats as other bacterial organisms such as *E. coli*, *Klebsiella* species, *Proteus* species and *Citrobacter* species were isolated. The presence of these bacterial organisms may be that the organisms were present in the raw chickens that were roasted or due to cross-infection during preparation, insufficient application of heat to the deep tissues and perhaps because of contamination from potential buyers, meat handlers; hands, napkins, trays, and the open air environment, Antiong and Udoh (1968) and Alonge & Oyekola (1982). These organisms could be pathogenic or opportunistic pathogens especially in infants or immunocompromised hosts or if they escape into other tissues outside the gut, Libby (1975) and Roberts (1984).

The average total viable aerobic bacterial load of 7.90×10^7 organisms per gram isolated from same-day prepared ready to eat chickens irrespectively of the pathogen potential of the organism calls for a closer attention in public health, though there is no yet a generally accepted standard for bacteriological safety. It implies that if about 200g of roasted chickens is consumed by an individual, such a person must then have ingested 1.58×10^{10} organisms out of which are potential pathogenic organisms.

Also, the average total viable aerobic bacterial load in the roasted chickens is higher than that reported by Alonge and Oyekola, (1982) which was 1.7×10^4 organisms per gram. This difference could be due to variation in the hygienic standards of the meat handlers, the utensil, slaughtering and plucking practices in these places, Alonge and Oyekola (1982). Also it could be due to massive build-up of bacteria in raw and roasted chicken because of improper washing, thawing, roasting and displaying of the meat, Pether & Gilbert (1971).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, based on the result of this investigation and in view of inadequate hygienic methods in use, it is considered that the roasted chickens sold at road sides in Jos could constitute an actual health risk.

It is therefore recommended that necessary health talks be organized to educate the meat handlers on the proper and hygienic methods of processing and displaying the roasted chickens.

REFERENCES

- Alonge O.D and Oyekola O.D (1982): The public health aspects of roasted chickens sold at take away shops in Ibadan, Nigeria. *Journal of Hygiene, Epidemiology, Microbiology and Immunology*. 26(1): 44-48.
- Anon (1990), Vigilana de gastroenteritis (1988-1990): *Bol. Microbial. Sem.* 5;35-36.
- Antiong O.A and Udoh E.U (1968); Roasted chicken: How safe? *Journal of Hygiene*. 2:18-21.
- Collee J.G and Marr. W (1996): Culture of bacteria. In *Mackie and Macartney practical medical microbiology* (14th ed) ELBS and Churchillstone vol. 1 pp120
- Collee J.G, Miles R.S and Watt B.(1996): Tests for identification of bacteria. In *Mackie and Macartney practical medical microbiology* (14th ed) ELBS and Churchillstone vol. 1 pp131-132
- Frobsiher and Feuts. M. (1982): *Microbiology in health and disease* (15th ed). Published by W.B Sanders Company, Canada. 360.372
- Gianella R.A (1981): Pathogenesis of acute bacterial diarrhoeal disorders. *Ann. Rev. Med.* 32:341-357
- Libby J.A (1975): *Meat Hygiene* (12th ed) Lea and Febiger Philadelphia. Pp 281-284

Carol Okoli *et al*: Continental J. Biomedical Sciences 1: 11 - 15, 2007

Old D.C (1996): Salmonella. In *Mackie and MaCartney practical medical microbiology* (14th ed) ELBS and Churchillstone Vol.1 pp385-400.

Oluyemi J.A and Robert F.A (1979): *Poultry production in Warm and Wet climates* (1st ed). Macmillan Press Ltd. Pp3-116

Pether J.V and Gilbert R.J (1971): Hygienic status of meat handlers in Spain. *J. Hygiene.* 69:673-681.

Plateau State of Nigeria Land and Survey Report 1999

Roberts D. (1984): Public health of roasted meat. *J. Hygiene.* 70: 585-588.

Sheffield. F (1996): Qualification in microbiology. In *Mackie and MaCartney practical medical microbiology* (14th ed) ELBS and Churchillstone. Vol1 pp 856-858.

Vernon T, Huber T.W and Thomas W. (1984): *Pathogenic microbiology* (3rd ed). J.B Lippincott Publishing Co. New York Pp318-330.

Received for Publication: 18/10/2007

Accepted for Publication: 22/12/2007

Corresponding Author:

Carol Okoli

P.O. Box 10664, Jos Nigeria

E-mail; Caroalph@yahoo.com